

Facets of Micro Financing In India

Dr. Sandeep Vij

Assistant Professor, Department of Management,
Lovely School of Business, Lovely Professional University, Jalandhar.

profsandeepvij@gmail.com

Monika Uppal

Lecturer, Department of Management,
Lovely School of Business, Lovely Professional University, Jalandhar.

monika.uppal123@gmail.com

Abstract

Financial inclusion is the biggest challenge being faced by financial system in rural India nowadays; and lack in the rural financial infrastructural support is adding to the gravity of the situation. Micro Financing is seen as a probable solution to this challenge. It has been regarded as the win-win formula for the financial institutions as well as the clients. The government has always relied on huge capital based nationalized banks for the promotion of financial inclusion in rural India; instead of micro financing institutions (MFIs). This study outlines the milestones in the growth of Micro Financing in India. It analyses the role of Micro Financial Institutions in providing cheap and prompt access to financial services in the rural terrain so as to facilitate the massive untapped rural population. It suggests that with a more enabling environment and surge in economic growth, the next few years promise to be exciting for the delivery of financial services to the poor in India. In the phase of recent recession and world wide financial crisis, the banks and financial institutions are emphasizing lending through micro financing , as the default rate is very low in case of lending through Self Help Groups (SHGs). This business model also helps to achieve the broader economic objective of financial inclusion.

Key words: Micro financing, Self Help Groups, MFIs

Introduction

According to a 1995 World Bank estimate, in most developing countries the formal financial system reaches only the top 25% of the economically active population - the bottom 75% have no access to financial services apart from moneylenders (**Kalavathi and Villalan, 2008**). Almost all the Governments came up with the number of lucrative schemes full of great packages of grants and subsidies for poverty alleviation. Though the purpose may be to attract the vote bank but there were continuous efforts as far as all the political parties are concerned. The research has proved that these mandatory programs implemented through banking infrastructure has never been interpreted by the banks as the profitable and the commercial activity and thus never been encouraged. Through the determined efforts, the Government of India is able to expand the formal credit base to the rural poor tremendously but it is infeasible to expect from the banks, possessing the limited resources, to manage the large number of the customer base with the smaller credit needs, frequent and urgent demands accompanied by almost zero collaterals to offer. The system of lending through Self Help Groups has emerged as the innovative tool to provide the profitable business to banks as well as credit to the weaker section of the society.

Micro finance refers to the provision of financial services to low-income clients for the business and other personal needs. It addresses a full range of banking needs for poor people. More broadly, it refers to a movement that envisions a world in which as many poor and near-poor households as possible have permanent access to an appropriate range of high quality financial services, including not just credit but also savings, insurance, and fund transfers.¹ Those who promote micro finance generally believe that such access will help poor people to get rid of poverty.

Vijay Mahajan, Managing Director of BASICS, estimated that 90 million farm holdings, 30 million non-agricultural enterprises and 50 million landless households in India collectively need approx US\$30 billion credit annually. This is about 5% of India's GDP and does not seem an unreasonable estimate (**Arora, 2005**). A World Bank study assessing access to financial institutions found that amongst rural households in Andhra Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh, 59% lack access to deposit account and 78% lack access to credit. Many of business management gurus have suggested the need for any type organizations to learn and be adaptive with environment as

¹ <http://profile.iiita.ac.in/IMB2008005/Microfinance.pdf>

they grow and expand (**Hartungi, 2007**).

Muhammad Yunus suggested that in Bangladesh 80% of the poor are covered under microfinance. The remaining 20% are expected to be covered with in next two years. India has been able to cover only 20% people under it and needs to be speed up (**Sharma, 2009**). The July 2003 Microbanking Bulletin reports that the institutions that reach out mainly to poor clients incurred operational expenses, that were, on average about 60 percent of the total loan amount given. Personal expenses made just under half of that (**Noponen, 2005**). India has the huge population under the poverty line which requires the direct measures for their financial inclusion in order to provide the equal opportunity to grow.

Rationale behind Micro Financing

Micro financing has established a ‘win-win’ proposition for all the parties concerned in the business. On one hand, government is successful in establishing the social balance by providing an independent life to the poor in the villages who are always under the shadow of scarcity of the resources and on the other hand, banks are achieving their market targets by widening their customer base managed effectively through MFIs and NGOs who are able to meet their objective of ensuring the equal financial opportunities to the poor.

Micro financing has provided the cheaper finance to the poor. The bottom section of the society who was exploited by the moneylenders in the region is served by the mechanism of micro financing. The reasonable interest rates with zero collateral have invited the even poorest families to invest in the viable business opportunities which could get them out of the clutches of the poverty and forceful starvations. Microfinance has drawn attention to bottom-lined borrowers who had been poorly served by the formal financial sector since the days of independence.

Financing through SHGs reduces transaction costs for both lenders and borrowers. While lenders have to handle only a single SHG account instead of a large number of small-sized individual accounts and the borrower is relieved of the expenses of traveling, burden of paper work and loss of effective workdays because it is divided among the group members.

MF refers to access to small loans without physical collateral. The loans are basically granted to the poor, especially the women, while encouraging them to save regularly. No surety or the collaterals are required for the loans disbursements. This has lead to the increase in the physical and mental independence among the male-dominated weaker section of the society. MFIs consist

of Refinance Institutions, Banks, Non Government Organisations and Self Help Groups dealing with small loans and deposits in rural, semi urban or urban areas enabling people to raise savings, productive investments and thereby their standard of living (**Nadarajan and Ponnuragan, 2006**). The products are designed as per the personal needs of the region under coverage.

It generates jobs and self-employment to many. This is the right time for the micro finance movement in India. It can be an answer to the critical situation resulted by financial crisis. For the overall growth of the country, rural India is required to be facilitated with the resources scarce at their disposal and Micro financing is ensuring that financial coverage. Since the financial sector has improved with the parallel improvement in the standard of living of the people below poverty line by increased level of savings and investment in the economy and the reduction in the level of unemployment. Micro financing is emerging as the panacea for prevailing social evils in India.

Micro Financing in India

The first major micro credit programme introduced in 1992 constituted only 500 Self-Help Groups. The micro credit programme in India is now the largest in the world.² NABARD introduced SHG-Bank linkage Programme in 1992 aiming to develop the financial independence in the poor societies by the availability of the banking funds on the security of their mutual deposits. The big milestones for Micro Financing in India turned out to be the establishment of Rashtriya Mahila Kosh in 1998 by the Govt. of India, establishment of MF Development Fund and establishment of SIDBI foundation in 2000 and bill on micro finance regulations introduced in parliament in 2007. Since the last few years the Govt. has taken major steps for the development of the sector through the providing the institutional framework and announcing the subsidies necessary for the promotions. RBI and NABARD act and active response in the financial sector for this emerging business venture which acted as the 'Win-Win' proposition in its successful models in India. Moreover NGOs and other privately owned institutes functioning at the route level are the major contributors which are indulged in developing the environment conducive for the growth of the micro mechanism. Institute of Financial Management and Research (IFMR) based in Chennai is leading the race for promoting the research and

experimentation in the field of Micro Financing. Banking sector in India is not far behind in the line as the banking sector specifically nationalised banks have the wider coverage in the area. The programs initiated by the Govt. are implemented through the well defined infrastructural base developed in the banking sector. In India, 400 million people spread across more than six million villages are estimated to be in need of micro-financing. The organized financial sector caters to the need of about 20 million people. The Global Summit on Micro Finance held in Washington in Feb '97 set a global target of covering 100 million poor families with credit by 2005 - it was expected that 25-30 million of these could be in India alone.³

Since 1991, the rates of interest were left for the discretion of the banks in the lending provided by the banks to the micro credit institutions and from MFIs to SHGs. But the ceiling continued for the direct lending by the banks to individual borrowers. The banks were given the full freedom to decide the micro product with the due consideration to the ground realities faced by them. They can design the product size, time period and other terms and conditions which could enlarge the market base. The recent estimate suggests that Indian microfinance currently reaches just about 4% of the poor directly through credit services (**Islam, 2009**). There are three trends in India: 1) There are increasing evidences that the poor is not being served in large number, especially in north and east. 2) The micro finance institutions that have accessed commercially oriented equity financing are moving, either consciously or not, away from serving the poor who are more expensive to reach, thereby reducing profitability. 3) There are a few MFI 'Biggies' that dominate the market, leaving the more innovative and younger organizations to struggle to grow in order to maximize their impact (**Meehan, 2009**).

Various examples are visible in India which proved the existence of micro financing at the larger and admirable level. **Amul** (Anand Milk Union Limited), formed in 1946, is a dairy cooperative movement in India. It is a brand managed by an apex cooperative organisation, Gujarat Co-operative Milk Marketing Federation Ltd. (GCMMF), which today is jointly owned by some 2.8 million milk producers in Gujrat. Every day Amul collects 447,000 litres of milk from 2.12 million farmers (many illiterate), converts the milk into branded, packaged products, and delivers goods worth Rs 6 crore (Rs 60 million) to over 500,000 retail outlets across the country. Amul's product range includes milk powders, milk, butter, ghee, cheese and others into

² <http://sibmfortright.blogspot.com/2006/11/microfinance-in-india.html>

³ <http://sibmfortright.blogspot.com/2006/11/microfinance-in-india.html>

soft drinks and ice creams. The products are available in over 500,000 retail outlets across India through its network of over 3,500 distributors. There are 47 depots with dry and cold warehouses to buffer inventory of the entire range of products.⁴

SKS India, launched in 1998, is the one of the fastest growing micro finance institution in the world. It has provided over Rs 6,212 crore and having maintained loans outstanding Rs. 2,216 crore to 3,906,007 women members in the poor regions of the country. Per month they are adding 2.5 million customers and are targeting 15 million customers by the end of the financial year 2012. In terms of growth the rate is 200% **(Ravindranath, 2009)**. Certain innovative initiatives are also in the pipeline for the rural masses. Banks make the tie ups with the companies for providing finance to facilitate the purchase of the essential goods by the poor repayable in installments. These products could be phones, water purifiers and solar light etc. which otherwise do not fall within their reach. Spandana founded in 1998 is also one of the fastest expanding MFI in the country. It has also proved its efficiency with the operating expense ratio of 5.5% on the portfolio. It now boasts of the client base which consists of almost 1.5% of the BPL population of the India **(Ravindranath, 2009)**. Another initiative is SEWA. It is a trade union of the poor women workers registered in 1972. Initially it provided the financial and social security to women laborers in the state of Gujarat. But now it is registered as a national union with seven sister SEWAs constituting its membership. These are SEWA Madhya Pradesh, SEWA Bihar, SEWA Uttar Pradesh, SEWA Delhi, SEWA Rajasthan and SEWA Kerala. In addition, SEWA has helped or is associated with workers' movements in other countries. Bandhan, based in West Bengal, is started as a Capacity Building Institution (CBI) in November 2000 and opened its first microfinance branch at Bagnan in Howrah district of West Bengal in July 2002. Today it has grown as strong as 412 branches across 6 states of the country. The organization had recorded a growth rate of 500% in the year 2003-04 and 611% in the year 2004-05. Till date, it has disbursed a total of Rs. 587 crores among almost 7 lakh poor women. Loan outstanding stands at Rs. 221 crores. Bandhan has staff strength of more than 2130 employees.⁵ They are operating in nineteen districts of West Bengal, two districts of Tripura, six districts of Assam and one district each in Bihar and Jharkhand.⁶

⁴ <http://www.citehr.com/189883-case-study-dairy-giant-amul.html>

⁵ www.bandhanmf.com

⁶ http://www.bandhanmf.com/download_file/ANNUAL%20REPORT%202006-07.pdf

There are various recent landmarks also setting the latest examples in the field of micro financing. Membership of Sa-Dhan (a leading association) has expanded from 43 to 96 Community Development Finance Institutions during 2001-04. During the same period, loans outstanding of these member MFIs have gone up from US\$15 million to US\$101 million. The CARE CASHE Programme took on the challenge of working with small NGO-MFIs and community owned-managed microfinance organisations. Outreach has expanded from 39,000 to around 300,000 women members over 2001-05, Many of the 26 CASHE partners and another 136 community organisations these NGO-MFIs work with, represent the next level of emerging MFIs and some of these are already dealing with ICICI Bank and ABN Amro. The outreach of SHARE Microfin Limited, for instance, grew from 1,875 to 86,905 members between 2000 and 2005 and its loan portfolio has grown from US\$0.47 million to US\$40 million (**Arora, 2006**).

Nowadays the big commercial banks are entering the micro credit business boosted by the success of the small credit institutes run by their own members without any financial subsidies and reliefs from the Govt. ICICI will work in collaboration with SKS to promote micro financing through MFI- SHGs model.

SHGs: A Complete Mechanism

The structure of Micro credit consists of Govt., credit unions, specialised banks or even commercial banks, MFIs, NGOs (Non Governmental Organisations) and SHGs. Lending models may vary depending upon the needs of the market but the basic framework is characterized as the collateral-free lending with reasonable rates of interest with the facility of easy repayments. In most of the cases the repayment period is smaller as compare to the other lendings by the bank. The purpose of the lending may range from the commercial to the personal needs of the disadvantageous section of the society.

The poor in the far flung areas are being benefited by Micro Financing through the formation of the Self Help Groups. The groups jointly generate a pool of the funds by collecting the fixed monthly deposits from the members of the group. The group can start functioning even with ten members. Maximum membership allowed is twenty because the no. of members beyond the limit will affect the basic functioning of the group and the level of co-ordination among them. In each group there are three office bearers- President, Secretary and Cashier conducting all the affairs starting from the collection of monthly installments to the payment of the loans to the

members and repaying the monthly loan installment to the bank. The president is the main office bearer who controls all the affairs like arranging the monthly meetings, depositing the monthly deposits into the bank account, condemning any group member who is violating the provisions of the group etc. Secretary is the second authority who assists the president and acts in the absence of the latter. The cashier takes into account all the affairs related with cash i.e. statement of collections and the statement of the disbursement made to the members in form of loans.

General Findings

The Bharat Microfinance Report - Quick Data 2009 reveals that Indian microfinance has reached out to 86.2 million clients and the portfolio outstanding of Rs. 351 billion including MFI channel actual data and SBLP estimated data for March 2009. Out of this MFI channel client outreach has grown at 60 per cent in 2009 against 41 per cent in 2008.⁷

“No doubts, India is one of the dynamic microfinance markets in the World”

-Jennifer Meehan, CEO, Asia region for Grameen foundation (**Meehan, 2009**)

Microfinance emerged as a noble substitute for informal credit and an effective and powerful instrument for poverty reduction among people who are economically active but financially constrained and vulnerable in various countries (**Varman, 2008**). As per Microfinance Information Exchange, Inc. (MIX) 2006-07 benchmark data, MFIs across the globe raised the capital from the various sources that includes 36.2% from borrowings, 35.8% from deposits, 15.5% from equity, 9.9% from debt including concessionary loans and compulsory savings, and 2.5% from donations. Thus the substantial capital raised by the MFIs was derived from the deposits (**Mohapatra, 2009**).

The banks used to avoid the financial services to clients due to limited margins. Banks is required to incur substantial costs to manage a client account regardless of the amount involved. For example, the total revenue from delivering one hundred loans worth \$1,000 each will not differ greatly from the revenue that results from delivering one loan of \$100,000. There is fixed cost for processing the loans because of which banks prefer the higher loans over the smaller ones leaving them with higher margins in their hands. There is a break-even point in providing loans or deposits below which banks lose money on each transaction they make. Poor people

⁷ The Bharat Microfinance Report – Quick Data 2009, Microfinance India, July 15, 2009; URL: www.indiamicrofinance.com/microfinance/microfinance-india/the-bharat-microfinance-report-quick-data2009.html

usually fall below it.

Poor can't offer the attractive collaterals for bank loans. There is strong requirement of the security for raising the funds from the big lenders in the country i.e. Commercial Banks. Poor generally fail to satisfy the essential requirement for credit. Because of these semantic obstacles they prefer to borrow from relatives or local moneylenders with a very high interest rate. The moneylenders had retained the major share of the market with their flexible service base which proved to be convenient, fast and very effective when borrowers are trapped into the problems. Defeating them in the business requires planned and determined steps by the Govt. to reach even to the places where the coverage of MFIs is growing.

The source of funds for MFIs varies within the industry. As per Microfinance Information Exchange, Inc. (MIX) 2006-07 benchmark data, MFIs across the globe raised the capital from the various sources that includes 36.2% from borrowings, 35.8% from deposits, 15.5% from equity, 9.9% from debt including concessionary loans and compulsory savings, and 2.5% from donations. Thus the substantial capital raised by the MFIs was derived from the deposits.⁸

Most of the development schemes lack the long term perspective. Some of the schemes are launched by the Govt. from time to time for providing relief to the suffering people at the bottom levels due to various natural and manmade disasters. The farmers are given the relief by waiving up their present loans. That has not only harmed the present financial sector in the economy but for the future the farmers are given the incentive for not paying the loans in time and pressurizing the Govt. for the waivers (**Yunus, 2009**). It could be a good strategy for the collection of the votes but cannot be regarded as the viable financial decision. The solution could be the extension of the term of the loan. In addition the Govt. may eliminate the interest for the remaining period giving the further relief.

Most of the credit has been availed by the disadvantaged section of the society. The proportion of women clients is 80% in the current year. MFIs served 7.7 million clients from SC/ST and minority community background.⁹ It has facilitated the credit support to the groups which remain away from the organized financial network due to various bottlenecks present in

⁸www.solutionexchange-un.net.in/.../1122-Strategies-to-Combat-Financial-Crisis-through-Innovative-Microfinance-Initiatives.html

⁹ The Bharat Microfinance Report – Quick Data 2009, Microfinance India, July 15, 2009; URL: <http://www.indiamicrofinance.com/microfinance/microfinance-india/the-bharat-microfinance-report-quick-data-2009.html>

the system.

Good recovery rate is the major booster for the market. Banks are successful in getting the recovery rate up to hundred percent (approx.) in micro financing. Most of the CEOs of the commercial banks and MFIs have claimed the full recovery rate. The social security plays as the binding in the case of group lending. The borrowed funds are also fetching good return from the business ventures in which poor invested. They are able leave with good margins even after paying the high interest rates. A survey conducted by RBI finds that the raising the loans from the MFIs is very easy for the poor. They have the close monitoring towards the system for ensuring that there is no default. MFIs have the good recovery rate. District administrations have the satisfactory views for the functioning of MFIs in their limits (**Ravindranath, 2009**).

High rates of interest play a negative role in the development. The rates of interest charged by the Commercial banks are very high in comparison to the loans provided for other purposes. Sometimes it goes beyond 20% p.a. also. The lending in case of micro financing needs the proper channels feedback, developing which is the costly affair for the banks which do not even have their presence felt in various villages. Due to heavy cost involved for setting up the infrastructural base, some of the large MFIs are also forced to charge the exorbitant rates of interests. No doubt, the interest charged by the commercial banks and MFIs is definitely lesser than the return fetch by the moneylenders and the other easy financing sources availed by the poor in the villages. But for the success of the microfinancing, the funds should be made available at the cheaper rates of interest.

The Positive approach by the banking sector is being injected in the system. The approach towards the Micro financing is changing due to the factor that the banks are desirous of expanding the operations in the rural areas also and they are encouraged due to the inherent features present in the mechanism. The banks have developed the positive views for the MFIs when they practically start working with them. They started considering them as the good business facilitators and correspondents. But the attitude favourable for the growth of MFIs has not gained much of the strength. The only limiting factor is the increased costs of operations for lending to SHGs but the increased coverage area can limit this cost also.

Bottlenecks for Micro financing in India:

In the 2000s, the microfinance industry's objective was to satisfy the unsatisfied demand on a

much larger scale as the major step in reducing poverty. Last few years have been successful in developing a commercial microfinance sector in India but several issues remain unattended before the industry will be able to satisfy massive national demand. The obstacles or challenges to build a sound commercial microfinance industry include:

Internal Factors

There are various factors prevailing in the system which are playing against the growth in the sector. All the internal parties to the mechanism i.e. SHGs, NGOs and MFIs must contribute for fulfilling the social cause with full integrity and honesty.

MFIs are perceived as the non- professional organizations i.e. unfit to invest in. They ran from the pole to the pillar in order to arrange the sufficient funds for their operations. MFIs are often not perceived as the most professional organizations as the big industrial houses and the commercial banks are. In reality they suffer from the limitations of the limited management capacity, Institutional inefficiencies etc. as a result MFIs find it difficult to arrange the loans and obtain the other financial incentives and support from the financial institutions.

MFIs in India often try to imitate the successful models in the other countries. MFIs need to be more regions specific and innovative. It requires the adoption of agricultural microfinance methodologies which will provide them the competitive edge for reaching the poor in the far flung areas where the commercial banks have the nominal coverage. They required to be served better not generated by the efforts of the poor being served but at the initiative of the lending hands by creating the existing and future demands for the products so designed for the purpose.

The bottom level is not aware of the innovative financial option. The second side of the picture is also not very encouraging. The problem lies in the fact that the financial services are boosted for those who are not even aware of their growth options. Few thinkers in the field are negative for the growth of the micro financing in the northern regions of India because the male dominance in the society prevents the women to step out of the house and form the groups in the rural areas and in the urban areas there is no homogeneity in the society and the system of trust and honor on which the foundations of repayment and low defaults are built. But to scale up and really make a difference to those outside the normal banking channels, microfinance institutions need to innovate.

MFIs are not able to give a drastic change in the rural India. Except certain regions, the lifestyle and livelihoods of the rural poor in the long run are least affected but it has certainly facilitated a boost to the borrowing levels of banks and ensuring them the larger margins and consumer market to target upon. These days MFIs in some of the lesser developed states of India are facing the criticism due to unsuccessful models followed. The products failed to meet the specific local demands. The people fail to trust the system due to various factors which are mostly attributed to the MFIs in India.

External factors

Govt. and the commercial banks acting as the direct lenders to the mechanism are considered external support for the growth of micro financing in India. There is need for the encouraging environment as well to let the system take its own pace for growth. A tiny segment of US\$30 billion potential market has been reached so far and this is unlikely to be addressed by MFIs and NGOs alone. Reaching this market requires serious capital, technology and human resources. However, 80% of the financial sector is still controlled by public sector institutions (**Arora, 2009**).

The group members are facing various semantic barriers and administrative obstacles since their inception. The barriers came from the illiteracy and non co-operative behavior of the poor group members. The loans are generally disbursed late due to procedural delays by the banks. The poor group members have to compromise with their daily wages to make regular visits to the banks for the approval of the loans. The daily workers survive on the day's earnings, the loss of which will force them to starve for the day.

Non-existence of a well developed and conducive policy environment to prevail into. As put up by Mr. Vikram Akula, SKS Micro Finance, the three key issues that a micro finance institution usually faces are lack of capital, the lack of capacity and the high cost of transaction. These limitations restrict the path of growth for the microfinancing in India.¹⁰

The growth of micro financing sector is badly hampered due to the personalized efforts required by the concerned institution. The collections centers are required in the huge numbers because of the limited lending radius of only two square kilometers. The officer is

¹⁰ <http://shantanudutta.sulekha.com/blog/post/2008/05/the-new-money-plant.htm>

required to approach all the borrowers personally on daily basis for which he is responsible. Mostly big banks can't afford the routine visits and huge expenses in the scenario where the business is coming to them in the urban areas with the reasonably good returns (**Ravindranath, 2009**).

The challenge lies in maintaining the remote branches and making all the information available on time. The rural branches are being setup by the banks for the better reach to the remote areas. With the broadband, no doubt, the problem has been solved to a greater extent but the banks are not able to ensure fully hi-tech branches due to financial constraints. The problem lies in the recruitment and quality of service provided by the banks also. The banks try to recruit the local residents as the employees in the branches situated in the far flung areas. These people, though less educated, will be able to understand their inmates and will ensure the efficient services.

There is the existence of bureaucratic hurdles. Various obstacles are coming in the way for the development of the micro financing. There takes a lot of time and labour to set up and run a new branch. And the banks are sometimes forced to set and follow such principles, under the political influence, as bench marks for which they are unwilling to give in. Due to the political interference the basic cause of the micro financing campaign has disappeared. The privileged section is served under the Governmental efforts in place of the deserving section of the society.

Raising the funds from the banks is also difficult for even the developed and fully grown up MFIs. Equity standing as the surety for NBFCs has made it as the preference for the banks in extending the loans to them but in case of MFIs and SHGs, their credit worthiness is doubted due to quality, profitability, governance and viability of the business model. Due to the scarcity of the funds they are forced to restrict their area of coverage.

The rates of interest charged are quite high. The rate are very high as compare to the other loan products of the banking sector, typically 12 to 30 per cent, mainly on account of the high transaction cost for the average sized loan. More coverage and increased customer base will allow these rates to be reasonable. Banks have the advantage over the MFIs because they can avail the benefit of the large scale and have the better competitive advantage also. The high cost of making small loans, relatively in more frequency to the poor section and without the sufficient collaterals are few main causes because of which banks do not actively participate in the development of the SHGs and the MFIs. These are not considered the profitable ventures by

banks due to the presence of structural rigidities and overheads involved.

There is a lack of proper implementation mechanism. Micro-finance programs have often been implemented by large banks at government behest and they are least interested since these are not considered profitable avenues. There is no separate mechanism to specifically deal with the micro financing which can be entrusted the task of developing the new and innovative schemes for the development and ensuring its effective implementation.

The govt. has not promoted any donor subsidies for the fund providers in the mechanism. Due to unsupportive infrastructural base, the poor MFIs having the least social and business contacts find it difficult to raise the sufficient funds necessary for the survival. Corruption is prevalent which raises the cost of financial transactions. Basic infrastructure and public services are not available which add to the burden on financial firms. The firms do not have any information about the financial status of their clients.

The law in India does not support the establishment of the Grameen banks. There is a restriction on the non acceptance of the deposits. Thus the establishments specifically constituted for the promotion of a social cause is always fighting for funds. The work also suffers because their primary target becomes the gathering of the pool of resources than serving the economy. The capacity in India becomes limited on the basis that these organizations can never be self dependent (Yunus, 2009).

Recommendations for Improvement

The system requires the joint effort from all the parties concerned for the improvement and the wider reach. The mechanism, itself, is very strong and demands no further improvements but still the benefits are not being extended to the poor and deserving population and thus not been able to eradicate poverty from the routes.

A. For Banks

Banks will have to rethink the system as a profitable avenue. The system is required to be developed innovatively based on the models suitable on the Indian soils. The banks are to support the system existing in the rural areas by various public or private hands. The successful collaborations of the commercial banks with MFIs and NGOs, operating at the route level having

the direct approach to the beneficiaries, can lead to profitable business proposition for the banks. This can provide a larger customer base ahead to their regular users for putting the excess money with the bank into the effective use. Bank will have to accept the reality that it is the large untapped market with almost zero default risk. The institutions directly dealing with the poor families should be approached for the better and safer reach to the soils of the land.

B. For MFIs

The micro financing should be handled as the business proposition not as the charity. MFIs should charge interest on the loans to cover their transaction costs. The funds provided for the investments in the local business propositions should be charged adequately so that interest accrued on these funds could be paid by MFIs to the lending financial institutions. That will make the system self-fed and not dependent upon the Govt. and other subsidies. More efforts must be devoted for keeping the transaction cost as low as possible and to reduce the interest rates also.

Perceptions towards MFIs need to be revised. The slow growth in micro financing is not the function of the shortcomings present in the mechanism but the perceived inadequate profitability and the insufficient administration in the MFIs. We can not ignore the deficiencies present in the system acting as the major hurdles for the success but the change of attitude of the Govt., big financial houses, people at large can surely renovate the system. Due to lack of technical support system MFIs are unable to ensure the satisfied level of services in the rural areas. The innovative and region specific schemes are required to be developed for the system to be declared as the success in the particular region. MFIs are required to develop the models on the basis of the characteristics and financial needs of the members to be served. The southern parts of the country will certainly differ in terms of the financial requirements, timings of the lending and their paying capacity in comparison to the northern parts of the country.

The MFIs should observe the ethical conduct in the business of micro financing which is the mantra for its success. The poor; facing the scarcity of resources, forced to observe the starvations on regular basis and on the most cheated by the money lenders and suffered through the institutional bureaucracy; fails to trust any system specifically designed at the initiative of the Govt. Thus the MFIs need to gain the confidence of the disadvantaged section of the society by

providing the transparent policies and effective utilisation of the funds raised from them.

C. For Govt.

MFIs should be allowed to mobilise savings in order to gain the self dependency. Savings could be a very feasible solution particularly in the long run. Various SHG Federations are being registered but require the freedom for the collection of the deposits from the members also which could be the great source for their funding. The legal framework should be so designed to make the MFIs self-fed institutions. They should not be burdened for looking at the hands of the Govt. for declaring the subsidies. There should be exemption for the license fee in case the ownership is in the hands of the borrowers. The self dependency of the mechanism will automatically take the growth path as the financing function will not be performed at the cost of efficiency in the service. MFIs should be self sustaining, be allowed to attract deposits, provide insurance and pension fund and should be capacity building as stated by Yunus (**Sharma, 2009**).

There is a need for a national level SHG federation. This issue always waited for the approval but failed due to lack of professionalism and political interference. The factors like cost efficiency, democratic government and close to hundred percent rate of recovery also failed to develop the interest in the masses. The local and national governments also have an important role to play in ensuring the growth and improvement of micro finance. The state wise groups could also be formed with the primary responsibility of developing the support system with the SHGs and NGOs operated at the route level actually facing with the shortcomings in the system. This will facilitate them to pick up the areas of the improvements. The policy environment could be made more supportive and to clear up misperceptions.

Credit rating of the MFIs and SHG Federation can be the solution for generating the confidence. The existing set up of micro financing is lacking the encouragement and financial support from the financial pillars of the country. The credit rating will also facilitate the mobilization of the deposits by the rated MFIs. That could generate the authenticity in the system. Specific credit rating agencies can be assigned the work of rating the MFIs on the basis of internal management, borrowers' base, quantum of lending etc.

There should not be any regulations on the interest rate. It should be a self-guiding mechanism based on the supply and demand conditions in the market. The efforts should rather be directed towards making the interest rates lower by increasing the customer base, establishing

a strong chain among the banks, MFIs and the SHGs and increasing the level of competition in this market. There should not be any scope for individual profits in MFIs. All the profits should be reinvested for meeting the costs of the transactions and for the growth in the long run.

A separate regulator designed specifically to cater the needs of the sector is required. There should be a separate regulatory authority for MFIs as distinguished in character from that for the commercial banks. The regulatory authority for MFIs should evolve guidelines keeping in view the objectives of social-economic development of the poor (**Sharma, 2009**). The representatives of the serving institutes should be present at the ground to attend listen and innovate for the most advantage to those at the ground. That can only make their efforts more socially responsive. The partnering with SHGs and MFIs with reasonable cost of funding by the banks has been seen as a more optimal approach till now

Transparency and the competition must be encouraged. More involvement of the financial institutions will generate the competition in the poverty funding market which will lead to automatic reduction of the interest rates and will result into customer friendly services. The ultimate benefit will play in the favour of the needy people. The growth of the system is the function of the confidence of the public into the system.

Increase in the customer base is the solution for the high cost of funding. A collective effort is required from all the parties either at the planning stage i.e. Govt., commercial banks or at the implementation stage i.e. MFIs, SHGs and the poor who are to be served. Firstly some basic infrastructural support is to be provided by the govt. which will encourage the further investment in the field.

References

- Arora (2009), "The Future of Microfinance in India: The Microfinance India Conference and a Look at an Expanding Market", Financial Sector Team, Policy Division, DFID available at URL: http://www.uncdf.org/english/microfinance/pubs/newsletter/pages/2005_06/news_in_dia.php
- Islam, A (2009) "The Desirability of Capping the interest Rate on Microfinance Loans", The Management Accountant, Vol 44, no. 3, pp 210-212. Hartungi, R (2007) "Understanding the Success Factors of Micro-finance Institution in a Developing Country." International Journal of Social Economics 34, No. 6, pp 388-401.
- Kalavathi, M.S. and Villalan, T.K.S., Impact of Micro Credit on Employment, Income and Poverty. Available at URL: http://www.ignou.ac.in/schools/sooss/FINAL_SOSS_CONFERENCE/full_%20papers/D3/M.S.Kalavathi.pdf
- Meehan, J. (2009). "Outreach Should Broaden". Microfinance World, April 2009, pp 13-14.
- Mohapatra, A. (2009), "The Impact of Financial Crisis on Microfinance." Microfinance World, April 2009, pp 23-24.
- Noponen, H. (2005) "Illustrations Help Extend Microfinance." Appropriate technology Vol 32, no. 2, pp 63-65.
- Ravindranath, S. (2009) "Small is Profitable", Microfinance World, April, 2009, pp 14-15.
- Sharma, A.B. (2009), "The success of microfinance in India", Microfinance World, April, 2009, pp 4-8.
- Srivastava, A. (2009); "Financial Literacy and Credit Counseling In India: A Road Map", Management Accountant, Vol. 44, No.4, pp 310-315.
- Varman, P.M. (2008) "Benchmarking Micro Finance Institutions in India and Determinants of Their Technical Efficiency." Indian Journal of Economics and Business, Dec. 2008, pp 22-25.
- Yunus, M. (2009). "Let's Now Ask Banks who is Credit Worthy: The Rich Who don't Pay Back or The Poor who Do" MicroFinance World, April 2009, pp 10-12.